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Stakeholders Contribution to Infrastructure Development in Enhancement of Girls Academic Achievement in Kenya: A Case Study of Siaya County

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ABSTRACT

The desire to have quality education for all Kenyan children is one of the concerns of Education. Stakeholders in education such as principals, religious sponsors, parents, politicians and Boards of Management play a key role in addressing this concern. Notwithstanding this concern the girl child's education is usually easily compromised compared with that of the boy child. The study therefore aimed at establishing the contribution of stakeholders to infrastructure development for the provision of quality education to girls in public secondary schools in Siaya County. The objective of the study was to establish the extent to which stakeholders contribute to the development of infrastructure in enhancement of girls' academic achievement in secondary schools in Siaya County. The findings of the study were that parents, principals and Boards of Management contributed highly to school infrastructure development while politicians' and religious sponsors' contribution was low. Nevertheless all stakeholders as partners in school infrastructure development contributed moderately to the development. The principals' ratings were higher than those of the teachers. In essence the stakeholders contributed to quality education as infrastructure is one of the determinants of provision of quality education. Findings of this study are significant to education managers in improving infrastructure in order to promote standards of girls education, help educational policy makers come up with policies that may retain the girl child in school, will make parents know their roles of providing teaching learning resources and will make parents, and motivates religious sponsors on the need to source for funds to improve girl child in secondary schools.

Key Words: Stakeholders, Contribution, Infrastructure Development, Enhancement, Girls Academic Achievement, Siaya, Kenya.

INTRODUCTION

The Ministry of Education (2005) states that the government is fully committed to an education system that guarantees the right of every learner quality and relevant education. It is in this light that the ministry of education deemed it necessary to improve its inspection wing by restricting it and changing its name from the inspectorate to Directorate of Quality Assurance and Standards (Ministry of Education Science and Technology, 2004). At school level principals and deputy principals are the designated internal quality assurance officers and at departmental levels the head of departments are the designated quality assurance and Standards Officers (Ministry of Education, Science and Technology, 2004). School prefects are mandated to assist school administrators in carrying out duties and responsibilities that enhance quality of education in Kenya. Those duties and responsibilities include supervision of curriculum activities such as preps lesson attendants by subject teachers. School infrastructure affects quantitative growth and the provision of quality education since a certain minimum space in a classroom per learner, adequate science rooms, well stocked library, recreational facilities and boarding facilities are pre-requisite in providing quality education in Girls Secondary Education. According to World Bank (2005), if the world is to achieve Education For All and Millennium Development Goals such as universal primary education by 2015, there is serious need for individual nations to develop holistic education sector plans and allocate sufficient national budgetary resources to develop related school infrastructure for quality education. Adequacy of school infrastructure is not only a problem in Africa, but also in the whole world. Many schools in Kenya are suffering from incidences of peeling paint, crumbling plaster, leaking roofs, poor lighting, inadequate ventilation and inoperative heating and cooling systems among other problems that limit provision of qualitative education.

According to Bregman and Stallmeister (2001) the struggle to achieve quality education for girls still remains a major concern in many countries in sub-Saharan Africa and it is overshadowed by other pressing and urgent educational needs. UNESCO (2002) observed that the introduction of modern technology in Egyptian Secondary Schools where each classroom was equipped with computer sets, overhead projectors and high speed internet resulted to improved performance. The government's increased allocation of resources toward education sector is further evidence that the government is concerned with the provision of quality education. The government allocates about 40% of her total recurrent expenditure on education (Republic of Kenya, 2003). Subsequently, the government appointed a presidential working party on education and training in 1988 to study the education sector and recommend ways of ensuring the delivery of education and training services, within the limits of the constrained economic conditions (Republic of Kenya, 1988 a). The report recommended the introduction of cost sharing in education by the government and other stakeholders like parents and local communities. The report was accepted by the government in Sessional Paper No.6 on Education and Training for the next decade and beyond (Republic of Kenya, 1988 b). The Government of Kenya has heavily invested in various interventions geared towards expanding school infrastructure which include the introduction of Constituency Development Fund in 2003, the Laboratory Equipment Fund in 2004, and School Infrastructure Development Fund in 2008 (Republic of Kenya, 2008). Due to financial constraints facing Kenya's education system as a result of reduction of government budgetary allocation, it would be necessary to assess the stakeholders' contribution to infrastructure development of Girls secondary schools and its influence on academic achievement in Siaya County which seems not to be doing very well. According to Bondo District Development plan of 2008 -2012, there are low education standards which have close relationship with understaffing in schools, lack of enough classrooms, dormitories, toilets (Republic of Kenya, 2009). The plan recommends serious need to rehabilitation of water supplies and sanitation facilities. The same challenge is also echoed in Siaya District Development Plan 2008 -2012 that reports that there are overstretched facilities for both teachers and students. The development plan also explains that it is important for stakeholders to provide infrastructure like buildings and address poor workmanship and misappropriation of funds.

Research objective

To establish stakeholders' contribution to infrastructure development in enhancement of girls academic achievement in secondary education in Siaya County.

SYNTHESIS OF LITERATURE ON INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT IN ENHANCEMENT OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

According to a survey report by Jeffry (2008) on cleanliness and learning in higher education in Boston, there is high correlation between levels of cleanliness and academic achievement indicating that clean environment promotes learning. While UNESCO (2005) also established that colour influences students' attitudes, behavior and learning particularly students' attention span. A carefully planned colour scheme can influence absenteeism, promote positive feelings about the school and also can influence muscular tension and motor control quite necessary in learning. Housing the teachers/learners in the school compound goes a long way to improve learner performance. She further observed that teachers who stay in the school compound can get time to help learners after classes through remedial teaching sessions in the evening. It also helps the learners to save their energy and time. Fisher (2006) in his study on the impact of school infrastructure on student outcomes and behavior in Georgia, established that academic achievement improves with improved building conditions, lighting levels, air quality and temperature. He further established that a correlation between school class size and student achievements. Having large classes can affect the quality of teaching as the teacher cannot provide individual attention as well as frequently evaluate learning. World Bank (2003) also emphasize that it is qualitative to teach small classes since it is easy to maintain class control and teachers can diversify their lesson according to the diverse capacity of their students. In Ghana, the working and living environment for teachers and students is below expectation. Schools in many counties lack basic amenities such as piped water, electricity, staffrooms and toilets. Housing is a major issue for nearly all teachers – only 30% of teachers were housed by 2003 (Akeyeampong, 2003). In Kenya, the Ministry of Education Science and Technology in 2005 identified critical issues relating to infrastructure as: Major backlog of infrastructure provision and shortage of permanent classrooms, existing school infrastructure is in poor condition, poor construction standard, inadequate maintenance, poor water system and sanitation. Such critical issues are contained in the previous reports and commissions such as the Kamunge Report (1988 a), Sessional Paper No. 6 and the Koech Report (1999). They have all placed importance on the provision of school infrastructure.

Stakeholders in the education sector, including development partners, play crucial contribution in supplementing the voted Government expenditures in education. Devolved funds such as the Constituency Development Fund have notable impact in constructing and renovating school facilities and providing water, electricity and other services. The private sector and religious organizations also complement government efforts in the provision of educational services at different levels of the educational system (Republic of Kenya, 2009). According to Khaemba and Okemo (2007) the universities have developed their infrastructure in efforts to develop quality academic performance. For instance, Kenyatta University has introduced fiber optic cable to ensure quality teaching. All Kenyan Universities have introduced information and communication technology infrastructure towards effective teaching/learning. Oriedo (2011) noted that schools that ensure that the students access clean water and sanitation facilities do promote the teaching/learning process hence increasing chances of doing well in their final examinations. Mutuko (2010) explains that increased funding is needed for quality education. He reveals that dismal performance in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education emanates from lack of adequate housing for teachers. He notes with regret that due to the impassable roads during the rainy seasons, teachers are forced to report on duty late and leave early. He argues that the scenario compromises on the academic standards in the area since most of the time, learners and teachers are not together to discuss academic matters. Sambili (2008) noted that housing plays a critical contribution to the achievement of the Kenya vision 2030. Poor environmental factors affect all learners. However, girls have special needs. Especially during puberty period, which if not provided for, the girls' academic achievement will be dismal. Such facilities are toilets, latrines with adequate privacy and water for girls' comfortable stay in school and learning (FAWE, 2002). Infrastructure such as improved lighting system; good meals eaten from a clean environment, lead to retention and good academic achievement. He looked at factors that mitigate against retention and academic achievement. Gogo (2002) findings in Rachuonyo District on the impact of cost sharing on access to secondary education established that class size of between 30 to 60 students is relatively modest in enhancing learning in secondary education. In addition, he further established that poorly equipped classrooms, laboratories, libraries, home science rooms and workshops make the learners fail to do the necessary practice thus affecting mastery of content as well as leading to poor performance. Sambili (2008) and Mutuko (2010) looked at critical role of housing to academic achievement. They agree in their findings that housing teachers in the school compound enables teachers to have more time with students hence increasing contact hours which contributes to good academic achievement. They did not look at the role of stakeholders to provision of infrastructure and therefore present study looked into the contribution of parents, Board of Management and religious sponsors in enhancing girls' quality education.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework (Figure 1) shows the contribution of stakeholders as the independent variables and infrastructure development as dependent variables. In Kenya under cost sharing policy in education various stakeholders in education are charged with the responsibility of contributing to the development of infrastructure in educational institutions. That is, they are partners with the government in providing the required infrastructure for enhancement of quality education. In fact, these stakeholders contribute three quarters of the required financial resources in the development of infrastructure. It can therefore be asserted that the government complements their effort besides providing other resources like human resource for enhancement of quality education.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework on stakeholders' contribution to quality Education in Public Girls Secondary Schools in Siaya County

There is no hard and fast rule on what exactly each stakeholder is expected to contribute. For instance, the politician is expected to contribute to Land, Latrines/Washrooms, Teaching and Non teaching staff Houses, Water, Electricity, Libraries, hostels/Dining halls and administration/ Tuition blocks in proportions depending on his ability and jurisdiction. Similarly, other stakeholders are expected to contribute the same in the same manner. It is the responsibility of Institutional, Boards of Management to make proposals and request the stakeholders to participate accordingly. For the parents, it is more less mandatory such that more often than not it is indicated in their fee structures for every year. Parents who fail to pay for the stipulated projects are considered violating the institutional requirements and therefore their children are excluded from the institutions temporarily or permanently despite the government pledge that they should not be excluded. The consequences are that the quality of education is compromised.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey design was used in this study. This is because descriptive survey allows is easy application of research instruments such as questionnaires and interview schedules which also allow for the collection of data from large number of respondents in a relatively short period of time with minimum cost. The population consisted of 20 head teachers, 20 deputy head teachers, 20 heads of examinations, 40 form four class teachers, 20 Board of Management chairmen, 20 Parents Teachers Association chairmen, 6 Sub County Quality Assurance and Standards Officers and 4 church education secretaries. Saturated sampling technique was used to select 18 head teachers, 18 deputy head teachers, 18 heads of examinations, 36 form four class teachers, 18 Boards of Management chairmen, 18 Parents Teachers Association chairmen, 5 Sub County Quality Assurance and Standards Officers and 3 church education secretaries. Data was collected by use of questionnaires and interview schedules. To ensure face and content validity of the research instruments, experts in educational administration were consulted and their input incorporated. Mean ratings were used to establish the level of contribution while t-Test was used to establish the significant difference between means of principals and teachers to make the study conclusive on all aspects of contribution. Reliability of the instruments was determined by piloting the instruments in two girls' secondary schools which constituted 10% of the population. Data collected by questionnaire was analyzed using descriptive statistics in the form of percentages, means and frequency counts;and inferential statistics, that is t-test while qualitative data from interviews and open ended questions was transcribed, organized into categories and sub categories and reported on an ongoing process as they emerged.

RESULTS

Research Question

The research question responded to was: What is the contribution of stakeholders in secondary education to infrastructure development in enhancing girl child's academic achievement in Siaya County, Kenya?

The principals and teachers of girls' secondary schools in Siaya County were asked to rate the contribution of stakeholders to the infrastructure that enhances girl child's quality education. Their responses were as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Contribution of Politicians to School Infrastructure Development

Aspects of Contribution by Politicians RE	RES	N	Mean Rating	t-test
Land	P	16	1.31	t(49)=-1.16,p =.093
	T	35	1.91	
Teachers Houses	P	15	1.33	t(48)=-642,p =.524
	T	35	1.51	
Classrooms /Workshops	P	15	2.33	t(47)=.021,p =.983
	T	34	2.32	
Water	P	15	1.67	t(47)=-1.035,p =.306
	T	34	2.12	
Electricity	P	16	1.88	t(44)=-.216,p =.830
	T	30	1.97	
Non teaching staff houses	P	15	1.20	t(48)=-.1373,p =.176
	T	35	1.60	
Library	P	15	1.73	t(47)=-894,p =.376
	T	34	2.12	
Dining hall	P	15	2.20	t(48)=-.658,p =.514
	T	35	2.51	
Dormitories	P	16	2.38	t(46)=-.069,p =.946
	T	32	2.41	
Offices	P	15	1.93	t(44)=-.815,p =.419
	T	31	2.29	
Staffroom	P	15	1.73	t(46)=-1.478,p =146
	T	33	2.39	
Latrines	P	15	2.00	t(46)=.072,p =.943
	T	33	1.97	
Washrooms	P	15	1.87	t(48)=.649,p =.520
	T	35	1.63	

KEY: RES – Respondents P- Principals, T-teachers

Interpretation of Mean Ratings

1.00 -1.44 = Very Low

2.45 -3.44 = Moderate

1.45 -2.44 = Low

3.45 -4.44 = High

4.45 -5.0 = Very High

From Table 1 it can be noted that both principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of politicians to the development of infrastructure through provision of land was very low and low according to principals and teachers as their means were 1.31 and 1.91 respectively. No statistically significant difference was found ($t(50) = .578, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.31$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 1.91$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that politicians had little contribution when it came to land where schools were constructed. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of politicians to provision of teachers' houses was very low and low as their means were 1.33 and 1.51 respectively. No statistically significant difference was found ($t(48) = .642, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.33$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 1.51$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that politicians contribute very little to provision of teachers' houses. Both principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of politicians to provision of classrooms and workshops was low as their means were 2.33 and 2.32 respectively. No statistically significant difference was found ($t(47) = .021, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 2.33$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.32$). Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of politicians to provision of water in schools was low as their means were 1.67 and 2.12 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = -1.035, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.67$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.12$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that politicians contribute little to provision of water in schools.

Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of politicians to provision of electricity was low as their means were 1.88 and 1.97 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(44) = -2.16, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.88$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 1.97$). Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of politicians to development of houses for non teaching staff was very low and low as their means were 1.20 and 1.60 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(48) = -1.373, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.20$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 1.60$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that politicians contribute very little to the development of non teaching staff houses. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of politicians to development of school libraries was low as their means were 1.73 and 2.12 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = -0.894, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.73$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.12$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that politicians contribute very little to the development of libraries in schools. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of politicians to the development of dining hall was low as their means were 2.20 and 2.51 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(48) = -0.658, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 2.20$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.51$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that politicians contribute little to the development of dining hall in the schools.

Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of politicians to the development or construction of offices in schools was low as their means were 1.93 and 2.29 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(44) = -0.815, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.93$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.29$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that politicians contribute little to the development of offices. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of politicians to the development dormitories in schools was low as their means were 2.38 and 2.41 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(46) = -0.069, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 2.38$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.41$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that politicians contribute little to the development of dormitories in schools. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of politicians to the development of staffroom was low as their means were 1.73 and 2.39 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(46) = -1.478, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.73$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.39$). This means that principals and teachers indicated that politicians contribute very little to the development of staffrooms in the schools. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of politicians to the development of washrooms in the school was low as their means were 1.87 and 1.63 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(48) = 0.649, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.87$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 1.63$). This means that both principals contribute very little to the development of washrooms.

From Table 2 below it can be noted that both principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of religious sponsor to provision of land was moderate as the means were 3.29 and 3.19 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = 0.236, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 3.29$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.19$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that religious sponsors contribute averagely towards providing for the construction of schools. Principals and teachers indicated that contribution of religious sponsor to provision of teachers' houses was low as their means were 2.64 and 2.29 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = 0.843, P > .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 2.64$) was not significantly different from teachers ($M = 2.29$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that religious sponsors contribute little to provision of teachers' houses. Both Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of religious sponsor towards construction of classrooms was very low as their means were 1.46 and 2.29 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(42) = 2.461, P < .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.46$) was significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.29$). Principals and teachers indicated that contribution of religious sponsors to the provision of water to schools was very low as their means were 1.36 and 2.21 respectively. There was significance difference found ($t(46) = -2.451, p < .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.36$) was significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.21$). This means that the views of teachers was that religious sponsors supply water in schools while principals felt religious were not doing much to ensure water supply to their sponsored schools.

Table 2: Contribution of Religious Sponsors to School Infrastructure Development

Aspects of Contribution by Religious Sponsor	RES	N	Mean Ratings	t- test
Land	P	17	3.29	t(47)=.236,p =.814
	T	32	3.19	
Teachers Houses	P	14	2.64	t(47)=.843,p =.403
	T	35	2.29	
Classrooms /Workshops	P	13	1.46	t(42)=-2.461,p =.018
	T	31	2.29	
Water	P	14	1.36	t(46)=-2.451,p =.011
	T	34	2.21	
Electricity	P	14	1.29	t(47)=.236,p =.818
	T	29	1.93	
Non teaching staff houses	P	15	1.27	t(41)=-1.858,p =.070
	T	33	2.00	
Library	P	14	1.50	t(46)=-1.924,p =.061
	T	34	2.29	
Dining hall	P	14	1.36	t(46)=-2.048,p =.046
	T	35	2.29	
Dormitories	P	12	1.83	t(47)=-2.591,p =.013
	T	33	2.27	
Offices	P	15	1.60	t(43)=-1.084,p =.285
	T	32	2.09	
Staffroom	P	15	1.73	t(45)=-1.410,p =.165
	T	34	2.32	
Latrines	P	13	1.38	t(47)=-1.514,p =.137
	T	34	2.18	
Washrooms	P	14	1.36	t(46)=-1.329,p =.0190
	T	34	1.85	

KEY: RES – Respondents P- Principals, T-teachers

Interpretation of Mean Ratings

1.00 -1.44 = Very Low

1.45 -2.44 = Low

2.45 -3.44 = Moderate

3.45 -4.44 = High

4.45 -5.0 = Very High

Principals and teachers indicated had very little contribution towards supply of electricity to the schools as their means were 1.29 and 1.93 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = .236, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.29$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 1.93$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that religious sponsors contribute very little to supply electricity in their sponsored schools. Both principals and teachers indicated sponsors had very little contribution to development /construction of non teaching staff houses was very low as their means were 1.27 and 2.00 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(41) = -1.858, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.27$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.00$). This means that both principals and teachers contribute very little towards the development of non teaching staff. Principals and teachers indicated that the religious sponsors' contribution was very low as their means were 1.50 and 2.29 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(46) = -1.924, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.50$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.29$). Principals and teachers indicated that contribution of religious sponsor to provision of teachers' houses was low as their means were 2.64 and 2.29 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = .843, P > .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 2.64$) was not significantly different from teachers ($M = 2.29$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that religious sponsors contribute little to provision of teachers' houses. Both Principals and teachers indicated that the

contribution of religious sponsor towards construction of classrooms was very low as their means were 1.46 and 2.29 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(42) = 2.461, P < .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.46$) was significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.29$). Principals and teachers indicated that contribution of religious sponsors to the provision of water to schools was very low as their means were 1.36 and 2.21 respectively. There was significant difference found ($t(46) = -2.451, p < .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.36$) was significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.21$). This means that the views of teachers was that religious sponsors supply water in schools while principals felt religious were not doing much to ensure water supply to their sponsored schools.

Principals and teachers indicated had very little contribution towards supply of electricity to the schools as their means were 1.29 and 1.93 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = .236, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.29$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 1.93$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that religious sponsors contribute very little to supply electricity in their sponsored schools. Both principals and teachers indicated sponsors had very little contribution to development /construction of non teaching staff houses was very low as their means were 1.27 and 2.00 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(41) = -1.858, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.27$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.00$). This means that both principals and teachers contribute very little towards the development of non teaching staff. Principals and teachers indicated that the religious sponsors' contribution was very low as their means were 1.50 and 2.29 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(46) = -1.924, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.50$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.29$). Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of religious sponsors towards development of dining halls in their schools were very low and low as their means were 1.36 and 2.29 respectively. There was significant difference found ($t(46) = -2.048, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 1.36$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.29$).

Table 3: Contribution of Board of Management to School Infrastructure Development

Aspects of Contribution by Board of Management	RES	N	Mean Ratings	t-test
Land	P	17	3.71	$t(49) = -1.716, p = .093$
	T	33	3.70	
Teachers Houses	P	16	4.69	$t(48) = -.642, p = .524$
	T	36	3.39	
Classrooms /Workshops	P	15	4.53	$t(47) = .021, p = .983$
	T	35	3.74	
Water	P	15	4.27	$t(47) = -1.035, p = .306$
	T	35	3.77	
Electricity	P	17	4.24	$t(44) = -.216, p = .830$
	T	32	3.66	
Non teaching staff houses	P	16	3.31	$t(48) = -1.373, p = .176$
	T	35	3.03	
Library	P	16	4.13	$t(47) = -.894, p = .376$
	T	35	3.86	
Dining hall	P	16	4.13	$t(48) = -.658, p = .514$
	T	35	3.66	
Dormitories	P	15	4.13	$t(46) = -.069, p = .946$
	T	35	3.46	
Offices	P	17	4.18	$t(44) = -.815, p = .419$
	T	34	3.47	
Staffroom	P	16	4.13	$t(46) = -1.478, p = .146$
	T	36	3.64	
Latrines	P	15	4.00	$t(46) = .072, p = .943$
	T	36	3.64	
Washrooms	P	16	4.06	$t(48) = .649, p = .520$
	T	36	3.47	

KEY: RES – Respondents P- Principals, T-teachers

Interpretation of Mean Ratings

1.00-1.44 = Very Low
1.45 -2.44 = Low

2.45 -3.44 = Moderate

3.45 -4.44 = High

4.45 -5.0 = Very High

From Table 3 it can be noted that both principals and teachers indicated that contribution of Board of Management to provision of land was moderate as their means were 3.71 and 3.70 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(49) = 1.716, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 3.71$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.70$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that religious sponsors contribute averagely to provision of land. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of religious sponsors was high and moderate as their means were 4.69 and 3.39 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(48) = -.642, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 4.69$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.39$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that religious sponsors contribute a lot to construction of houses for teachers. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of Board of Management to the development of classes was high as their means were 4.53 and 3.74 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = .021, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 4.53$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.74$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that Board of Management members who were influential, used their positions to bring Constituency Development Funds to their schools hence more classes. Principal indicated that the contribution of Board of Management to provision of water was high and teachers' indication moderate as their means were 4.27 and 3.77 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = -1.035, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 4.27$) was significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.77$). This means the principals indicated that Board of Management contributes highly towards provision of water and teachers indicated that Board of Management contributes averagely towards the provision of water in schools.

Principals indicated that the contribution of Board of Management to provision of electricity was high and teachers indicated moderate as their means were 4.24 and 3.66 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(44) = -.216, P > .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 4.24$) was significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.66$). This means the principals indicated that Board of Management contributes highly towards the provision of electricity in schools while teachers indicated that the Board of Management contribute averagely towards the provision of electricity in schools. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of Board of Management to provision of non teaching staff houses was moderate as their means were 3.31 and 3.03 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(48) = -1.373, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 3.31$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.03$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that Board of Management contribute averagely to the provision of non teaching staff houses. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of Board of Management to the development of school library was high as their means were 4.13 and 3.86 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = -.894, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 4.13$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.86$). This means both principals and teachers indicated that Board of Management contribute highly towards the development of school libraries.

Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of Board of Management towards the construction of the dining hall was high as their means were 4.13 and 3.66 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(48) = .658, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 4.13$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.66$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that Board of Management's contribute highly to the construction of the dining hall in their schools. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of Board of Management to the development of dormitories was high as their means were 4.13 and 3.46 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(46) = -.069, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 4.13$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.46$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that Board of Management's contribute highly to the construction and maintenance of dormitories to ensure that students sleep in a clean environment. Principals indicated that the contribution of Board of Management on construction of offices was high while the teachers indicated moderate contribution towards the development of the offices as their means were 4.18 and 3.47 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(44) = -.815, P > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 4.18$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.47$). This means that both principals indicated that Board of Management had high contribution of development of offices in schools in order for the teachers to get where to sit and prepare for their lessons. Principals indicated that the contribution of Board of Management to the construction and maintenance of latrines was high while teachers indicated moderate. Their means were 4.00 and 3.64 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(46) = .072, p > .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 4.00$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.64$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that Board of Management contributes highly to the development of pit latrines.

Table 4 Contribution of Principals to School Infrastructure Development

Aspects of Contribution by Principal	RES	N	Mean Ratings	t-test
Land	P	16	3.50	t(47)= -1.675,p =.101
	T	33	2.79	
Teachers Houses	P	14	3.79	t(47)= -.647,p =.521
	T	35	3.49	
Classrooms /Workshops	P	15	4.00	t(48)=1.100,p =.277
	T	35	3.57	
Water	P	17	4.24	t(50)=2.571,p =.013
	T	35	3.34	
Electricity	P	17	4.00	t(46)= -.850,p =.400
	T	31	3.68	
Non teaching staff houses	P	14	3.93	t(48)= 2.137,p =.038
	T	36	2.89	
Library	P	16	4.00	t(49)= 1.439,p =.157
	T	35	3.49	
Dining hall	P	16	3.94	t(49)= 1.265,p =.212
	T	35	3.46	
Dormitories	P	14	3.86	t(47) =.434,p =.666
	T	35	3.69	
Offices	P	16	4.13	t(48) =1.704,p =.095
	T	34	3.50	
Staffroom	P	16	3.94	t(50) =.562,p =.577
	T	36	3.75	
Latrines	P	16	4.13	t(50) =.991,p =.326
	T	36	3.78	
Washrooms	P	16	4.00	t(49)=1.533,p =.132
	T	35	3.40	

KEY: RES – Respondents P- Principals, T-Teachers

Interpretation of Mean Ratings

1.00 -1.44 = Very Low

1.45 -2.44 = Low

2.45 -3.44 = Moderate

3.45 -4.44 = High

4.45 -5.0 = Very High

From Table 4 it can be noted that principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of principals to the availability of land for school construction or expansion was moderate as their means were 3.50 and 2.79 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = -1.675, p > .05$). The mean of the principal ($M = 3.50$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.79$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that Board of Management contributes moderately to get land for the school. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of principals to the development of teachers' houses in schools was moderate as their means were 3.79 and 3.49 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = -.647, P > .05$). The mean of the principal ($M = 3.79$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.49$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that principals contribute averagely to the development of teacher's houses in schools. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of principals to construction and maintenance of classrooms /workshops

was high as their means were 4.00 and 3.57 respectively. The mean of the principals ($M = 4.00$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.57$). No significant difference was found ($t(48) = 1.100, P > .05$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that principals contribute highly to establishment of classrooms /workshops. Principals indicated that the contribution of principals to the provision of clean water in schools was high and teachers indicated moderate. Their means were 4.24 and 3.34 respectively. Significant difference was found ($t(50) = 2.571, P < .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 4.24$) was significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.34$). This means that principals indicated that principals contribute highly to the provision of water while the teachers indicated moderate. Principals indicated that the contribution of principals to the provision of electricity was high and teachers moderate as their means were 4.00 and 3.68 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(46) = -.850, P < .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 4.00$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.68$). This means that principals and teachers indicated that principals control a lot to provision of electricity in schools. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of principals to the development of houses for non teaching staff was moderate and low as their means were 3.93 and 2.89. Significant difference was found ($t(48) = 2.137, P < .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 3.93$) was significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.89$). This means that principals contribute averagely to the development of houses for non teaching staff, while teachers indicated their contribution as low. The interview findings indicated that Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of principals to construction and maintenance of classrooms /workshops was high as their means were 4.00 and 3.57 respectively. The mean of the principals ($M = 4.00$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.57$). No significant difference was found ($t(48) = 1.100, P > .05$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that principals contribute highly to establishment of classrooms /workshops.

Principals indicated that the contribution of principals to the provision of clean water in schools was high and teachers indicated moderate. Their means were 4.24 and 3.34 respectively. Significant difference was found ($t(50) = 2.571, P < .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 4.24$) was significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.34$). This means that principals indicated that principals contribute highly to the provision of water while the teachers indicated moderate. Principals indicated that the contribution of principals to the provision of electricity was high and teachers moderate as their means were 4.00 and 3.68 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(46) = -.850, P < .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 4.00$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.68$). This means that principals and teachers indicated that principals control a lot to provision of electricity in schools. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of principals to the development of houses for non teaching staff was moderate and low as their means were 3.93 and 2.89. Significant difference was found ($t(48) = 2.137, P < .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 3.93$) was significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.89$). This means that principals contribute averagely to the development of houses for non teaching staff, while teachers indicated their contribution as low. The interview findings indicated that

Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of principals to the development of library was high as their means were 4.00 and 3.49 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(49) = 1.439, P < .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 4.00$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.49$). This means that principals and teachers indicated that principals contribute highly to the development of library. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of principals to provision of dining hall was moderate as their means were 3.94 and 3.46 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = .434, P < .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 3.94$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.46$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that principals contribute averagely to development of Dining halls in schools. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of principals to the development of dormitories was average as their means were 3.86 and 3.69 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = .434, P < .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 3.86$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.69$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that principals contribute moderately to the development of dormitories. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of principals to the construction of staffroom was moderate as their means were 3.94 and 3.75 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(50) = .562, P < .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 3.94$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.75$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that principals contribute moderately to the development of staffrooms. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of principals to the development of pit latrines was both high and moderate as their means were 4.13 and 3.78 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(50) = .991, P < .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 4.13$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 3.78$). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that principals contribute highly to the construction and maintenance of pit latrines.

Table 5: Contribution of Parents to School Infrastructure Development

Aspects of Contribution by Parents	RES	N	Mean Ratings	t-test
Land	P	17	3.53	t(48)=.025,p =.980
	T	33	2.58	
Teachers Houses	P	17	3.29	t(50)=3.706,p =.001
	T	36	2.75	
Classrooms /Workshops	P	15	3.73	t(48)=2.451,p =.018
	T	35	3.60	
Water	P	15	3.60	t(48)=1.337,p =.187
	T	35	3.43	
Electricity	P	16	3.69	t(47)=1.334,p =.189
	T	32	3.34	
Non teaching staff houses	P	14	3.21	t(49)=.548,p =.586
	T	35	2.86	
Library	P	17	3.94	t(49)=.678,p =.501
	T	35	3.23	
Dining hall	P	17	4.06	t(49)=1.248,p =.218
	T	36	3.36	
Dormitories	P	17	4.35	t(48)=1.633,p =.109
	T	35	3.71	
Offices	P	17	4.29	t(49)=1.849,p =.071
	T	34	3.18	
Staffroom	P	16	4.25	t(50)=1.329,p =.190
	T	36	3.47	
Latrines	P	16	4.50	t(49)=.896,p =.375
	T	36	3.42	
Washrooms	P	16	4.00	t(50)=1.517,p =.136
	T	36	3.19	

KEY: RES – Respondents P- Principals, T-teachers

Interpretation of Mean Ratings

1.00 -1.44 = Very Low

1.45 -2.44 = Low

2.45 -3.44 = Moderate

3.45 -4.44 = High

4.45 -5.0 = Very High

From Table 5 it can be noted that both principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of parents to availability of land was moderate as their means were 3.53 and 2.58 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(48) = .025, P > .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 3.53$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.58$). This means parents contribute moderately to the availability of school land. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of parents towards building of teachers' houses was moderate as their means were 3.29 and 2.75. Significant difference was found ($t(50) = 3.706, P > .05$). The mean of principals ($M = 3.29$) was significantly different from the mean of teachers ($M = 2.75$). This means that principals indicated that parents contribute moderately to the development /construction of teachers' houses and teachers indicated low contribution of parents to the construction of teachers' houses. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of parents to construction of classrooms /workshops was moderate as their means were 3.73 and 3.60 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(48) = 2.451, P < .05$). The mean of the principals ($M = 3.73$) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers

(M =3.60). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that parents contribute moderately to construct and maintain the existing classrooms and workshops. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of parents to the provision of water was moderate as their means were 3.60 and 3.43 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(48) = 1.337, P > .05$). The mean of the principals (M =3.60) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers (M =3.43). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that parents contribute moderately to the provision of water in the schools where their daughters learn.

Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of parents to provision of electricity was moderate as their means were 3.69 and 3.34 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(47) = 1.337, P > .05$). The mean of the principals (M =3.69) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers (M =3.34). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that parents contribute moderately to the provision of electricity. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of parents to provision of houses for non teaching staff was low as their means were 3.21 and 2.86 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(49) = .548, P > .05$). The mean of the principals (M =3.21) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers (M =2.86). This means that both principals and teachers indicated that parents contribute little to the provision of houses for non teaching staff. Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of parents to the development of libraries was average as their means were 3.94 and 3.23 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(49) = .678, P > .05$). The mean of principals (M =3.94) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers (M =3.23). This means both principals and teachers indicated that parents contribute satisfactorily towards the development of school libraries.

Principals and teachers indicated that the contribution of parents to the provision of dining hall was high and moderate as their means were 4.06 and 3.36 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(49) = 1.248, P > .05$). The mean of principals (M =4.06) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers (M =3.36). This means that the principals indicated that parents contribute highly to the contribution of dining halls while teachers indicated that parents only contribute moderately towards the provision of dining halls in the schools. Principals and teachers indicated high and moderate contribution of parents towards the development of the dormitories as their means were 4.35 and 3.71 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(48) = 1.633, P > .05$). The mean of the principals (M = 4.35) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers (M = 3.71). This means the principals indicated parents contribute highly to the development of dormitories while teachers said the parents contribute moderately to develop dormitories in schools. Principals and teachers indicated high and moderate contribution of parents towards the development of offices as their means were 4.29 and 3.18 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(49) = 1.849, P > .05$). The mean of the principals (M =4.29) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers (M =3.18). This means that principals indicated parents contribute highly to the development of offices while teachers indicated only moderate contribution of parents towards development of offices. Principals indicated that the contribution of parents towards the construction of pit latrines was high while teachers indicated moderate contribution as their means were 4.50 and 3.42 respectively. No significant difference was found ($t(49) = .896, P > .05$). The mean of the principals (M =4.50) was not significantly different from the mean of teachers (M =3.42).

To arrive at the conclusions on the stakeholders contribution to infrastructure development in enhancement of girls academic achievement in secondary schools in Siaya County the overall means, standard deviation and t-test were computed. The results were as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Overall means, Standard deviations and t-test output
Group Statistics

Respondent	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t- test
Score 1	1017	3.13	1.675	$t(1776) = 2.355, p = .019$
2	2246	2.93	1.465	

From Table 6, it can be observed that the overall mean for principals was 3.13 and for teachers 2.93. There was a significant difference between principals' overall mean and teachers' overall mean $t(1776) = 2.355, p < .05$. This means that the principals' overall mean was higher than that of teachers. It can be concluded that the principals were not in agreement with teachers on stakeholders contribution to infrastructure development in enhancement of girls academic achievement in Siaya County. In this respect, principals rating was higher than that of the teachers on the stakeholders' contribution. The principals are custodians of contributions made by stakeholders to the schools and therefore their rating is more realistic.

DISCUSSION

The interview findings indicated that politicians did not provide but only assisted or made little contribution to construction on the land donated by the community or religious sponsors. Document analysis indicated that in young schools, the land was bought by a group of elites from the community and gave it out for the construction of schools. The old schools whose land was donated first to the missionaries, the wealthy community members had changed. In fact one wealthy member of the community had grabbed a portion of the school compound of one of the schools. The principal contested in court but there was no solution to the problem since the school had no land title deed that could define the size of the land owned by the school hence the school lost its land. The study revealed that inadequate land for schools affected the students negatively. This was because 9(50%) of schools did not have playing fields in their school compounds. The games teachers make arrangement in the nearby primary schools to allow their students use the fields in primary school. The borrowing of use of field affected time management since the students could only start using the fields after 4.10pm as soon as primary school pupils left the compound. One deputy principal complained; "It is hard to keep time for classes in the evening because games teachers delayed students in the field." It was reported that some students went further without games or only stood around the fields as spectators due to lack of play fields. It was also reported that students who did not participate in active activity during games got exhausted at night hence affecting their studies whereby some would sleep during preps. The interview findings indicated that religious sponsors gave part of their compound towards construction of schools. The ten principals (56%) reported that their schools started from the church compound. In one school, the principal reported that the church had given their land space for keeping their four dairy cows. In terms of income and savings, the church contributes a lot since on some days students eat vegetables from their farm creating room for school to save what would have been used for buying vegetables. This contributes to quality education since the saved money can be used to purchase tuition materials. The interview findings indicated that Board of Management bought different pieces of land to enable the school to expand its compound. Five (28%) of the principals interviewed reported that land where the school expanded including the field was bought through harambees organized by the Board of Management. The thirteen (72%) of principals interviewed indicated that it was their Board of Management that passed resolution to get more land for their schools. This means the bigger the compound, the better for the students because they become physically fit. The interview findings indicated that principals being executive officers in the Board of Management, they were able to give valuable advice on how school could expand for purchase of more land. Indeed it was the agendas for the meeting hence enlightening the members of the board on the challenges facing the school in terms of size. The interview findings indicated that parents contributed through "harambees" to buy land towards the expansion of the school compound. Document analysis revealed that all parents were given 'Harambee' cards to raise money in order to buy more land for the school. The expansion of the school meant that there was even space for the field for students to go for games. This implied that the students were physically fit and mentally alert after running round their fields and this made their studies better as their absorption rate increased with activeness in the field.

The interview findings indicated that politicians do not provide the housing for teachers claiming that teachers have house allowance and should find elsewhere to stay. Document analysis revealed that on certain occasions, politicians criticized the teachers' stay in the compound. They even condemned the old houses in the compound where teachers were residing as good for demolition. This did not even go well with the teachers who felt they stayed there for security of the students. The interview findings indicated that religious sponsor of some schools allowed some teachers to stay in their church compound. Two principals 11% interviewed reported that they were staying in the houses given by the church that sponsors their schools. From the two schools, their Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education means were relatively high. One principal noted; "I am able to monitor both dawn and night preps since I stay within the compound." This means that students left on their own may not do their best without adult supervision. The study findings concurs with Beerli (2005) who observed that housing the teachers /learners in the school compound goes a long way to improve quality education. This is due to the fact teachers in the compound supervise preps enabling students to make good use of their study time without making noise. It was also observed that teachers who stay in the school compound can get time to help learners after classes through remedial teaching sessions in the evening. Staying in the school compound also helps the learners to save their energy and time. One principal noted; We clear the form four syllabus in March every and this normally gives the teachers a good time for envision. This has been possible because staying in the compound and start extra classes as early as 5.00am since teachers stay within the compound. The Deputy principal agreed with the view of the principal when she explained that even presence of the teachers in compound increases sense of concentration in the students since they fear the consequences of being court doing wrong things during preps. The interview findings indicated that principals do not repair and maintain the teacher's houses. This means the teachers who stayed in the school compound to help students during remedial lessons both at night preps and dawn preps were staying in dirty and poorly maintained houses. Document analysis revealed that the poor condition of teachers houses discouraged

teachers from remitting their house rents to schools. They felt they did not deserve to stay in such bad housing. This finding is in line with Akeyeampong (2003) who also observed that the working and living environment for teachers and students is below expectation. He explained that schools in many countries lack basic amenities such as piped water, electricity and toilets. He added that housing is a major issue for nearly all teachers where only 30% of teachers were housed by 2003 (Akeyeampong, 2003). The study revealed that where teachers stay in good housing, they had confidence and high level of commitment in helping the learners to improve their grades hence quality education. However in schools where principals did not care about teachers' housing, the teachers had heavy heart in going extra or giving extra work after the normal working hours. In agreement with this study, Mutuko (2010) explains that increased funding is needed for quality education. He reveals that dismal performance in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education emanates from lack of adequate housing for teachers. He notes with regret that bad roads during rainy seasons forced teachers to report on duty late and leave early. He argues that the scenario comprises on the academic standards since learners and teachers lack time to discuss academics. The interview findings indicated that teachers who occupied school houses paid for the maintenance. On the other side there was money for the development of the school being paid by parents and this may have been the reason why principals indicated moderate contribution by the parents. Document analysis revealed that principals even recover the money for rent from remedial money when teachers failed to pay their monthly rent. The implication of recovering money of rent from remedial money meant that the money was not being used for what it was meant for. Some teachers were not teaching during the extra remedial classes being mishandled. However when asked why they did not reunite their rents, they reported that houses had not been repaired and were in bad condition that did not deserve to be paid for. In one school, the teachers felt that the principal was eating their money while principal felt that the teachers did not deserve the money since they had not attended their remedial lessons. This implied that in a way contributed to low performance in some subjects where teachers were affected with the issue of rent.

The interview findings indicated that politicians through the Constituency Development Fund constructed the classes in the new schools. However they had not done much concerning workshops. Document analysis revealed that politicians relied so much on the Constituency Development Fund without their personal contribution towards the building of classrooms in the schools. The interview findings indicated that religious sponsor had not constructed any classroom for the students. In one school, the principal reported that the church had stopped them even from using a nursery classroom built as the church compound. This interfered with education since they were only learning under tree. Principals and teachers indicated that Board of Management members who were influential, used their positions to bring Constituency Development Fund funds to their schools hence more classes. Interviews also revealed that in one school, 120 students were taught computer in one room. The crowd interfered with both mastery and concentration. This happened because some students did not even know how to do basics like switching on the computer system as there with sixteen computers against 120 students. The findings of this study agrees with Gogo's whose research findings reveals that class size of between 30 to 60 students is relatively modest in enhancing proper learning in secondary schools (Gogo, 2002). He explained that poorly equipped workshops make the learners fail to do the necessary practice thus affecting mastery of content as well as leading to poor performance. The interview findings indicated that principals in most cases initiated the building of classrooms and the classrooms. In nine (50%) of schools visited the classrooms were well constructed and well maintained. The study revealed that good classrooms/workshops contributed to quality education as girls prefer good places. The study also found that female students do not like associating with bad environment particularly dirty and unrepaired classes. This lowered their self esteem hence academic achievement. In five (30%) of schools visited, the classrooms were poorly constructed with substandard materials. The classes were dusty and students not in a position to clean them using water. Such dirty interfered with the concentration of most students. However in 4(20%) of schools visited, it was found that classes were overcrowded with large number of students as high 75 students in one classroom. This further reduced their performance because teachers were not able to have full class control. This finding is consistent with the findings of Fisher (2006) who indicated that academic achievement improves with improved building conditions, lighting levels, air quality and temperature. He further established that large classes can affect the quality of teaching as the teacher cannot provide individual attention as well as frequently evaluate learning. It is also in line with World Bank (2003) that emphasize that it is qualitative to teach small classes since it is easy to maintain class control and teachers can diversify their lesson according to the diverse capacity of their students. The interview findings indicated that parents through the Parents Teachers Association chairmen make decisions on the projects to be developed in the school. In most cases, the Parents Teachers Association executive would agree on what to be constructed as a priority. Document analysis revealed that the Parents Teachers Association chairman even looked for the Guest of honour who contributed through the harambee where enough funds were raised to build classes in the school.

The interview findings indicated that politicians had constructed a bore hole in one school out eighteen schools.

Document analysis revealed that politicians even sent cheques that did not go through in the banks, a fact that did go well with the school principals hence indicated no contribution or very little contribution concerning provision of clean water in the schools. The interview findings indicated that in two (11%) the principals recorded that the church pumped water to teachers' houses and even to the kitchen. This saved time that students would have wasted to go to the river to carry water for cooking. They also made life for teachers easier time to spend more time with students. The interview findings indicated that Board of Management organized for fund raising to drill water. In another school the principal reported that the politicians through the Constituency Development Fund drilled water that stopped girls from going out to search for water. The study findings also revealed that girls need adequate water supply to comfortably do their cleaning in privacy. Bathrooms and pit latrines which are poorly maintained make girls get infections which interfere with their performance. In some cases, poor sanitation may affect girls and may cause them miss school. The study revealed that girls worried about cleanliness and may not concentrate when there is serious water shortage in the school. This finding can be supported by Maeke (2009) that water and sanitation is critical particularly among girls in schools and that more than 50% of primary drop out in Marsabit were due to inadequate water and sanitation. The findings also concur with Oriedo (2011) when he maintained that schools that adhere to the national school health policy and other initiatives that promote a clean and healthy learning environment and frequently engage students in discussions about health and ensure they access clean water and sanitation facilities promote the teaching /learning process hence increasing chances of high academic achievement in the national examinations. The interview findings indicated that the principals paid water bills in time to avoid any inconveniences brought by disconnection of water supply. The fact that the teachers had lower mean than that of the principals may mean that the teacher over expected or felt that there were enough resources but the principals were not doing much to drill water in the school compound.

The interview findings indicated that parents pay for provision of water. This happens through the promptness in payment of school levies. From interviews conducted with Sub county Quality Assurance and Standards Officer, it was established that some parents were prompt in payment of school levies while some of them were not prompt. He indicated from interviews; "Most of the parents will always pay school levies as early as required by the school. Some parents have even gone to the extent of paying a whole years' school levies so that the girl learns freely without interference to go for school levies every now and then. However there are some few parents who will only pay school levies once their girls have been sent from school several times. From the study it was realized that parents were not prompt in payment of school levies and therefore the principals were not able to pay for water bills in time. At times, water was disconnected due to nonpayment of bills. This implied that girls had to go looking for water outside the school compound. Lack of water in school would therefore lead to students wasting learning time looking for water or even queuing for water. This would finally interfere with quality education since girls value water so much in search that when it is lacking they stressed and partially absent during the lessons. The current findings are in agreement with Murillo and Roman (2011) who found that the availability of water has an effect on the achievement of primary education, but its relative weight varies significantly from country to country, whereas in South Africa it has been pointed out that government failure to provide water and sanitation is undermining the children's chances of obtaining good education. In the Eastern Cape, the Department of Education has stipulated that all schools must have water and sanitation for the improvement of education, while also in the Limpopo province, Mashamba (2004) stresses the importance of water supply in the improvement of education. However, it was observed that parents who were not prompt in payment of school levies affected quality education as sometimes girls delay for classes as they look for water.

Both principals and teachers indicated that politicians contribute little to provision of electricity in schools. The interview findings indicated that politicians gave a lot of promises that they did not come back to schools to fulfill their empty promises. Principals and teachers indicated that religious sponsors contribute very little to supply electricity in their sponsored schools. Interview findings indicated that religious sponsor did not even help the schools to get electricity. The interview findings indicated that Board of Management in their meeting prioritized the provision of electricity to enable girls get enough light during their night studies. The study revealed that availability of electricity in schools encourages increase contact between teachers and students since the teachers were even able to come back and mark assignments at night in their staffroom. However, schools without electricity, the teachers were using teaching time in the class to mark students' books since they were many to be carried home for working. The interview findings indicated that principals priorities the development of school such as electricity during Board of Management analysis revealed that documentary analysis revealed that principals write proposals looking for funds especially from Constituency Development Fund. This is because classroom lighting plays a particular critical role in student's performance. Obviously students cannot study unless lighting is adequate.

The study revealed that the performance of girls improved due to the availability of electricity. This was because the students were able to start their dawn preps as early as 4.00am and at night extend as late as 11.00pm. More hours of private studies enabled the students to discover more in their studies. Murillo and Roman (2011) concurs with the findings of the current study that the availability of electricity in the school has an effect on the

achievement of primary education. Schools providing basic facilities such as electricity perform much better in achievement growth than schools that did not. The study found out that the availability of electricity in schools enabled the students to extend their studies into the late nights and at dawn. Teachers also found it easy to extend making students book in the staffroom even at night. This implied that the presence of the teachers in the staffroom at night maintained students' discipline hence good academic achievement in their work. The interview findings indicated that parents through their payment of the development fund to schools, they also contributed to the development of electricity in schools. Document analysis revealed that parents contributed in kind when one parent even talked to the officers from power house so that power would be dropped in the school after the wiring was completed. Document analysis revealed that the schools' academic achievement went up after electricity that had been brought. This implied that electricity facilitates learning for students.

The interview findings indicated that politicians did not construct any house for non teaching staff. Document analysis did not reveal any contributions to the development of non –teaching staff houses. Interview findings did not reveal any contribution to the sponsor towards the development of the houses occupied by non teaching staff. The interview findings indicated that Board of Management ensured that the kitchen staff stays within the compound so that they start working as early as 5.00pm to prepare breakfast for the students. The other key person whose house was considered to be important in the school by the Board of Management was school matron so as to check of health condition of the students even in the night. Nine (50%) of the principals interviewed indicated that the board of management passed in their meetings that matrons and the kitchen staff be housed in the school compound since their services are required even during off hours. One deputy principal pointed out; "In our school, discipline begins with watchman to everybody. Cooks are never reminded of their duties hence early preparation of meals. This has enabled our school routine to work without any delay since all respect time." The study revealed that housing of non teaching staff especially cooks helped everybody in the school to be effective as students clear up from their residential to their classes early enough that contributed to quality learning. The interview findings indicated that principals tried to construct many small houses in the school compound to house at least the key non teaching staff who work until late. The study found out that in schools where cooks were not residing in the school, the students suffer particularly when they go for games and arrived in school during the nights when cooks have left the school compound. They had to serve themselves, others missing food and affecting their studies. Principals and teachers indicated that parents contribute little to the provision of houses for non teaching staff. The interview findings indicated that parents through their parental obligation were able to raise funds for the construction of non teaching staff houses. The interview findings indicated that principals tried to construct many small houses in the school compound to house at least the key non teaching staff who work until late. The study found out that in schools where cooks were not residing in the school, the students suffer particularly when they go for games and arrived in school during the nights when cooks have left the school compound. They had to serve themselves, others missing food and affecting their studies.

The interview findings indicated that politicians used their influences to source for textbooks in the libraries. However, these did not participate in the construction of any library. Religious sponsors contribution to library was very minimal. The interview findings indicated that no religious sponsor had constructed the library on its own. The interview findings indicated that Board of Management members volunteer to carry or donate books to stock the school libraries. Documentary analysis revealed that Board of Management members had donated a good number of textbooks to the libraries. One principal reported; "The Board of Management members approved funds for purchase of more textbooks during their meetings. Some members buy books using their own money and bring to school during book donations." The study established that adequate library services influenced the provision of quality secondary education. The study also found that sufficient supply of reference books promoted collaborative work and language development resulting to improved performance. The study also found out that libraries enable learners to research and make reference after the formal learning hence depending their understanding as well as performance. The study's finding is in agreement with Munda, Tanui and Kaberia (2010) who revealed that students in schools with adequate libraries tended to achieve higher average test scores. According to their study, libraries should be viewed as a vital partner in knowledge management that shares with all other instructional agents all other instructional agents, their responsibility for systematically designing, carrying out and evaluating the total process of learning and teaching hence a school system without a well stocked library will limit students' academic achievement and the level of exposure to current developments and trends in the world. Principals and teachers indicated that principals contribute highly to the development of library. The interview findings indicated that principals either organized harambee for construction of a school library or use the development fund paid through school fees to build the library in the school. The study revealed that libraries provide opportunity for teaching and student get more information to add to what has been taught in class. This has been supported by Odhiambo (2000) who maintains that textbooks provide the first reading experience to learners. Olendo (2008) argues that students' performance is affected by the quality of facilities such as well stocked libraries stand a better chance in performing well in examinations than those which poorly equipped. The study established that schools with well stocked libraries

did well in academic achievement. This implied that when students reading in the library have a wider knowledge of the subject content than the students that only go through their notes. It is therefore important to note that school libraries are vital in knowledge management as wide reading broadens the students knowledge hence she is able to argue out the points well.

The interview findings indicated that principals guide the Board of Management on the most basic facilities like Dining hall. It is through the initiative of principals that both Parents Teachers Association and Board of Management give priority to the construction of Dining hall in the school. The study revealed that schools with well developed and spacious dining halls saved time during the meals. Students eat all at once then run to class while those without dining hall students are forced to make long queues a factor that delays the first lessons after lunch because teachers have to wait for students a little longer. The interview findings indicated that religions did not build the dining hall but contributed during the harambees to construct one. The interview findings indicated that Board of Management members prioritized the building of new dining halls and expansion of the existing ones so that the students could eat in a spacious and clean environment. The study revealed that availability of dining hall in the school help the learner to eat well instead of eating while standing. One Head of Department lamented; "We have no central overtime after lunch because our students eat in shifts and sometimes finish late interfering with first lesson after lunch. Parents contribute to the development of schools' dining halls through the payment of Parents Teachers Association development funds. In this respect, one Board of Management chairperson stated "New parents paid Ksh. 8,000/- and parents for continuing students paid Kshs. 5,000 towards the building of the new dining hall." From the interviews conducted with Board of Management chairpersons, it was established that most parents were prompt in payment of the Parents Teachers Association development fund. The payment by parents implied that principals had ample time to purchase the building materials which were used in the construction of the new dining hall until the completion. From the findings of the study, principals, deputy principals, Head of Departments and form four class teachers indicated that the building or expansions of the existing dining hall affected the quality education of the students. This implied that all students would go for meals at once whenever the bell for meals goes and use only thirty minutes to eat and go back to class since the food was already served in the dining hall. This created enough time for the lunch time private reading before the afternoon lessons begin. The findings of this study is in line with Kereri (2003) who noted that good meals eaten from a clean environment, lead to retention and good academic achievement in schools of Kajiado Sub county.

Principals and teachers indicated that Board of Management's contribute highly to the construction and maintenance of dormitories to ensure that students sleep in a clean environment. However, in ten schools visited, the dormitories were not enough for the students. Some classrooms were turned into dormitories with triple dekaras around 10(60%) of schools. One deputy principal explained; "Our students squeeze a lot in their small dormitories. During rainy seasons, their sleep is disturbed due to roof leakages and during dry seasons, they sweat a lot due to overcrowding in the dorms. They wake up tired and even doze during dawn preps." The study found out that students especially girls need space for their privacy and this is lacking, it affects their learning. However, girls have special needs especially during puberty period, which is not provided for the academic achievement will be dismal such facilities are dormitories with adequate privacy for comfortable stay in school and learning (FAWE, 2002). The interview findings indicated that principals after identifying the dormitories as the project for development, they together with Parents Teachers Association executive identify the sources of fund that particular projects. Document analysis revealed that principals together with Parents Teachers Association chairmen mobilized parents to pay towards the construction of dormitories. The fact that there were good clean dormitories, it meant that the students would sleep well and wake up strong to start their new academic days. However in one school where the dormitories were lacking, the students complained of inadequate sleep during the training sessions. Lack of good sleep made them feel tired during their studies, hence poor academic performance. Parents contribute highly to the development of dormitories while teachers said the parents contribute moderately to develop dormitories in schools. The interview findings indicated that parents on many occasions raised money through harambees organized by the schools to get money for the expansion of the existing dormitories and the building of new ones. Document analysis revealed that both parents and their children were issued with harambee cards to collect funds for the construction of the new dormitories. Whenever a student or a parent or student failed to raise money indicated in the harambee card, such amount was transferred to school fees. This increased the school fee very high that some needy students dropped out of school since they could not raise the very high amount required by the school. One class teacher lamented; "Needy students seem to be brighter than others but many of them drop out of school when the school fee becomes too high for them." The study found that the increase in the development fund made fee unaffordable to the needy students. A factor that made them to take too at home waiting for fee and when they came back to school, they were not able to catch up with the syllabus coverage since a lot of content had been taught when they were away. The implication of raising fee school is that only those from the rich or advantaged families manage to raise fee and stay in school throughout while those from disadvantaged families lag behind in fee payment and this in turn affect their academic achievement hence affecting quality education of the entirely school negatively.

Politicians contribute little to the development of offices. The interview finding indicated that even schools that were started as early as 1975 did not even have an administration block. One classroom was being used by teachers as the staffroom while the principal's office was along the corridor of classes. Document analysis did not show any concern towards the development of offices in schools. The interview findings indicated that Board of Management members occasionally pass through the staffroom and other offices to Great teachers and this could also give them the opportunity to see whether the offices were in good conditions or not. Document analysis revealed that Board of Management members in their meeting discussed about the construction of various offices where the school administrators could attend to visitors. The study revealed that the availability of offices by the Board of Management improved the keeping of documents and even management of both internal and external examinations. In one school, the Deputy principal and Head of Department reported that one of their Board of Management members donated some computers that they were using in their offices. This enabled teachers even to keep their schemes of work in a soft copy where they could make some adjustments easily. The interview findings indicated that parents contribute a lot towards the development of offices through the payment of their Parents Teachers Association development fund which is paid yearly. The document analysis also revealed that Parents Teachers Association executives meet and prioritize the school projects which will always to one at a time.

The interview findings indicated that politicians through their Constituency Development Fund kitty contributed towards construction of pit latrines in only two schools. In one school, a cheque of Ksh. 300,000 was issued to the school administration when the only pit latrine sank. This money was economically spent to construct six door pit latrines. This money was only given from their emergency fund meaning they only came in during the crisis. In another school, the Constituency Development Fund gave Ksh. 500,000 for the construction of ten doors but the building sunk as soon as it was completed. Document analysis showed that the school administration had no say on which contractor to work in her school. This means the CDF brought their own person whom they gave instruction from outside and as long as he listened to their "voices" everything was "okay". Sixteen (88%) of the principals interviewed did not want anything to do with Constituency Development Fund funding pit latrines since the workmanship was bad and risky to the students. Document analysis revealed that Board of Management members use their influence to get money from constituency development fund for the development of their schools. Seven (40%) of schools visited the pit latrines were labeled Constituency Development Fund an indication that the money came from the devolved Constituency Development Fund. Principals indicated that parents contribute a lot to the development of pit latrines in the schools while teachers indicated parents contribute moderately towards the development of pit latrines in the schools. The interview findings indicated that principals identify and prioritize the projects such as construction of pit latrines. It is the principals who explain to the Board of Management the policies of Ministry of Education Science and Technology on the number of latrines needed for the school according to the ratio required. The study revealed that basic facilities like latrines facilitates the smooth running of the school. The findings of this study are in agreement with (UNICEF, 2004) that established that inadequate sanitation at school leads to lower attendance and is one of the reasons for girls in particular, miss school or drop out of school. The schools with high academic achievement scored highly in the availability of basic facilities in the form of toilets, academic achievement will be higher. The schools with lower cadmic achievement scored higher in terms of the unavailability of water and toilets. This implies that unavailability of toilets /latrines influences academic achievement negatively.

The interview findings indicated that there was no single washroom constructed by the politicians in any of the eighteen schools visited. There was no documentary pointing towards the development of any washrooms by politicians. Document analysis revealed that Board of Members use their influence to get money from constituency development fund for the development of their schools. Seven (40%) of schools visited the pit latrines were labeled Constituency Development Fund an indication that the money came from the devolved Constituency Development Fund.

CONCLUSION

School infrastructure influences the provision of quality education. The infrastructure that enhances girl child education include: land, teachers houses, classrooms /workshops, washrooms, electricity, non teaching staff houses, library, dining hall, dormitories, offices, staffroom, latrines and water. The number and quality of school infrastructure affect the provision of quality performance in girls' secondary schools. The stakeholders' contributions are made in accordance with proposals by the respective school managements. The contributions by parents, principals, and Board of Managements were rated high while those of politicians and religious sponsors were rated low.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Kenya government through the Ministry of Education Science and Technology should insist on the availability of infrastructural facilities by the stakeholders before a new school is registered.

Quality buildings, toilets and adequate electricity be made available in girls' secondary schools as they contribute to girls' quality education.

All stakeholders be encouraged to increase their contribution to infrastructure development so as to meet the threshold in enhancement of academic performance of girls.

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